

An AI/ML Proactive Network Service Relocation Approach for Multi-Admin Domain Scenarios

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Abstract—Novel networking paradigms are enabling the introduction of innovative vertical use cases and new business relations in the 5G/6G mobile ecosystem. For instance, a use case may require the coordination of domains owned by different operators to provide service continuity and keep offering a vertical network service (NS) in similar conditions after a cross-border situation. This demonstration presents a procedure to perform a proactive service relocation in such a multi-administrative domain scenario considering an automotive use case. This demonstration proposes a cloud-native solution combining multiple enablers to manage the life-cycle of virtualised automotive NSs. During run-time, and upon registration, an AI/ML-based enabler decides proactively on the service relocation moment based on the collected vehicle’s positions and triggers an Integration Fabric enabler following ETSI ZSM guidelines to start a new instance of such automotive NS at the associated ETSI NFV management and orchestration stack present in the neighbouring administrative domain.

Index Terms—Proactive Service Relocation, Multi-Domain, AI/ML, Cloud-Native, ZSM, NFV, MANO, Edge

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of new paradigms in the architecture and management of 5G/6G networks based on network softwarization, like Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV), is contributing towards its faster and more flexible transformation. This also allows the introduction of new stakeholders in the mobile network ecosystem, like the vertical industries, and enables new scenarios and business models.

An example of this can be found when applied to the automotive vertical industry, which proposes innovative use cases (UCs) related to Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) scenarios. Some of these use cases require low latency, which can be achieved when deploying the CAM network service (NS) backends in edge points of presence (PoPs) close to the end users. These possible UCs increases its complexity when considering cross-border scenarios, like in the 5G-ROUTES project [1]. In this situation, several mobile network operators need to cooperate so their management and orchestration (MANO) stacks are able to keep offering the CAM NS under similar conditions (e.g., required latency), thus offering

service continuity from an application perspective across the involved independent administrative domains (ADs) [2]. In recent years, several works have dealt with the instantiation of NSs in multiple ADs following the guidelines proposed by ETSI NFV working groups, e.g., [3], [4]. However such approaches considered static use cases in the sense that they do not consider mobility patterns associated with automotive scenarios, thus not deriving service relocation procedures. Such consideration is partially addressed in [5], also following ETSI NFV principles. However, in this approach, the CAM NS application needs to include the logic (e.g., track vehicle’s location) to trigger the service relocation.

Differently, our demonstration proposes the use of the so-called enablers to assist CAM NS applications. These enablers, proposed in the 5G-ROUTES project [1], are cloud-native solutions common to automotive NS applications that are designed to handle its life-cycle management (LCM) as well as to assist them during run-time. For instance, these enablers offer an interface that when combined, allows to achieve the required proactive service relocation in a transparent way to the CAM application. Briefly, the core enabler for this functionality is the Predictive Resource Allocation Enabler (PRAE), which predicts the cross-border based on AI/ML algorithms feed by the collected vehicle’s positions, determines the appropriate PoP for the new NS instance in the visiting AD and triggers its instantiation operation through a multi-domain Integration Fabric (IF) element based on ETSI ZSM guidelines. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first practical system performing an AI/ML-based proactive service relocation of automotive applications in a multi-AD scenario while combining ETSI NFV and ETSI ZSM guidelines.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 presents the experimental setup deployed for this demonstration in the CTTC 5G Lab (Castelldefels, Spain). It is distributed among three physical servers. One of them runs the Tenant Web Portal (TWP), which is a platform to trigger LCM operations (e.g., onboarding, instantiation, termination) of the available CAM UCs, as well as a tool to analyse and visualize the data obtained from the execution of UCs. The remaining servers implement the different ADs. Each server hosts two virtual machines containing i) an all-in-one Kubernetes cluster acting as a PoP and ii) an instance of Open

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Fig. 1. System Architecture under demonstration

Source MANO (OSM) Release 13 acting as an ETSI NFV orchestrator. In each of these servers, we run an instance of the CAM Services platform (CAM SP) defined within the 5G-ROUTES project [1]. The CAM SP is designed to run on top of the mobile infrastructure. It is a cloud-native solution that consists of a set of technological enablers (TEs) designed to perform the automated orchestration of CAM Services. These TEs also assist the CAM services during run-time to enhance its functionality in cross-border scenarios involving multiple ADs through interaction between TEs of different CAM SP instances running in neighbouring ADs.

In particular, in this demonstration, we focus on the interaction among four of these TEs to trigger the proactive service relocation of a CAM service instance in a new AD as the lead user of this CAM service moves between ADs. Namely, the involved TEs are the Integration Fabric (IF), the CAM Repository, the Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) Broker, and the Proactive Resource Allocation Enabler (PRAE).

The *IF* [7], based on ETSI ZSM architectural guidelines, consists of a message-passing broker based on the MQTT protocol and the Service Adapter (SA) module. The defined topic and message structure allow the exchange of orchestration operations across the associated brokers in the different ADs. The SA module subscribes to the corresponding topics of the broker, processes the operation and executes them by interacting with its associated OSM instance.

The *CAM Repository* is a registry management system handling and storing the required NS artefacts (i.e., container images, Helm chart definitions, and OSM VNF and NS descriptors). Among its functionalities [8], the CAM Repository relies on its unified artefact catalogue to provide information about the amount of resources (i.e., CPU, RAM, storage) required by a given kind of CAM NS.

The *V2X Broker* is a message-passing broker based on

MQTT/AMQP protocols allowing the exchange of V2X awareness messages (CAM/DENM/CPM) among vehicles in different ADs. Its topics are organised according to Quadtree tiles and an available GEO location sub-module performs the message distribution based on calculations over the defined Quadtree tiles, guaranteeing that vehicles can receive the messages of overlapping areas regardless of the V2X broker instance (belonging to any CAM SP) they are connected to.

The *PRAE* is the main decision actor in this process. This TE provides the proactive decision support for CAM Services requiring service relocation based on the information provided by the messages received from V2X Broker, querying resource information to CAM Repository and IF and finally triggering the LCM operation through the IF. It consists of two stages powered by AI/ML algorithms [6]. First, the *Future Location Prediction* stage uses a Dilated Convolutional Network trained with Deep Neuroevolution to forecast the position of the followed vehicle. If a border crossing is predicted, the *Optimization of Service Positioning Module* second stage uses a Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm with an Actor-Critic Deep Neural Network to determine the best PoP location to launch the new instance of the CAM Service in the next AD.

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the proactive relocation of a CAM NS across independent ADs thanks to the interactions of the mentioned TEs and OSM running in each CAM SP instance. This service relocation is proactively triggered by the trajectory evolution followed by the leading car of a sample see-through CAM UC considering a cross-border scenario, where a mobile network discontinuity will happen. This service relocation procedure aims to provide service continuity from the application perspective so the users can keep using the CAM service in the same conditions (i.e., experiencing reduced round-trip delay) after entering in the new AD. The

Fig. 2. CAM Service Relocation workflow in the CAM Services Platform

main steps of the demonstration depicted in Figure 2 are:

- 1) The NS owner interacts with the TWP to start an instance of the CAM Service backend in the selected geographical area of a given AD. This is possible because the corresponding network artefacts have been previously onboarded in both ADs, as explained in [8]. During this instantiation, the PRAE also decides the suitable PoP given the received request.
- 2) As part of its initialisation, the CAM Service backend registers its associated information (instance name, type of service and the UC leading vehicle identifier) in the PRAE, so it starts following its trajectory from the CAM messages collected from the V2X Broker.
- 3) Then, we start the SUMO [9] traffic simulation considered for this demonstration. It includes the border crossing of a road between Latvia and Estonia countries. The simulated vehicles send CAM messages to the V2X Broker with a periodicity of 1s to inform of its position.
- 4) PRAE filters these messages, considering only those of the registered leading vehicle, and runs its AI/ML-based algorithm to determine its position in the following time window.
- 5) Upon the prediction of a change of country of the leading vehicle, the PRAE module starts the service relocation process. First, PRAE determines the location of the new NS instance in the new domain and then, it triggers its instantiation, as explained in the next steps.
- 6) PRAE sends a message to the cross-AD topic of the IF to collect the resource availability (CPU, RAM, storage) and location of the PoPs in the following AD. PRAE also contacts the CAM Repository through the IF to collect information about the resource requirements (CPU, RAM, storage) of the type of CAM service under relocation. With this information, it runs the AI/ML-based algorithm to determine the suitable PoP in the next AD to run the new CAM NS instance.

- 7) PRAE warns the TWP about the cross-border event and sends a *"CreateNetworkServiceOperation"* to the cross-AD topic of the IF. The SA module of the IF in the other AD processes this message so the new CAM NS instance is available in the next AD when vehicles recover mobile connectivity after the border crossing.

During the demonstration, all steps are shown through the graphical user interface of TWP, OSMs, and the logs provided by the different TEs instances.

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